

Surgical Management of Vaginal Evisceration in a 66-Year-Old Patient at a Secondary Care Hospital: A Case Report

Ochoa Alvarado Xiomara Cristina*¹, Cetina Castillo Raúl Amilcar², Chávez González Héctor Alejandro³, Lendewig Barrera María Virginia⁴

¹Fourth-year General Surgery Resident, Hospital General de Cancún “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez”, Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social (IMSS-BIENESTAR). Faculty of Medicine, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán.

²General Surgery Attending, Hospital General de Cancún “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez”, Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social (IMSS-BIENESTAR).

³General Practitioner, Universidad Autónoma de Chihuahua.

⁴General Practitioner, Universidad Anáhuac.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Spontaneous vaginal evisceration is a rare clinical entity, particularly in patients without prior surgical history. Fewer than 100 cases have been reported in the literature, the first described by Hyernaux in 1864. Urgent surgical resolution is crucial to prevent complications such as intestinal obstruction, perforation, ischemia, sepsis, and death.

Case Report: A 66-year-old woman with no relevant medical or surgical history presented with spontaneous transvaginal evisceration of small bowel loops, without an apparent traumatic trigger. Emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed, with intestinal reduction and primary repair of the posterior vaginal wall defect. During the postoperative course, the patient developed intestinal obstruction, requiring reoperation, after which she recovered uneventfully. This case underscores the importance of prompt diagnosis and management to prevent complications such as obstruction, ischemia, perforation, necrosis, or sepsis in secondary care settings.

KEYWORDS: Spontaneous vaginal evisceration, vaginal rupture, vaginal atrophy, vaginal prolapse, vaginal wall defect.

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CASE PRESENTATION

A 66-year-old woman presented to the emergency department with a 24-hour history of spontaneous exposure of intestinal loops through the vaginal introitus, preceded by sudden-onset abdominal pain. She denied previous episodes, trauma, or signs of genital prolapse. Her only past medical history was hypertension. She had no surgical history and reported four full-term, uncomplicated vaginal deliveries.

On examination, the patient was alert and hemodynamically stable, with no signs of acute abdomen. Bowel sounds were absent. Approximately 40 cm of free, edematous small bowel loops protruded through the vaginal introitus, without signs of necrosis or perforation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Transvaginal evisceration of edematous small bowel loops. Image obtained from the clinical record, Hospital General de Cancún.

Surgical Management of Vaginal Evisceration in a 66-Year-Old Patient at a Secondary Care Hospital: A Case Report

Laboratory values: hemoglobin 14.2 g/dL, leukocytosis $11.9 \times 10^9/L$, glucose 65 mg/dL, creatinine 1.2 mg/dL, lactate 0.8 mmol/L.

The loops were irrigated with sterile saline, and an attempt at manual reduction into the peritoneal cavity was unsuccessful due to edema. The bowel was covered with sterile moist dressings, and the patient underwent emergency midline exploratory laparotomy. A 7 cm defect was identified in the posterior vaginal wall (Fig. 2), with no inflammatory or neoplastic changes. Uterus and pelvic support ligaments were normal.

Fig. 2. Posterior vaginal wall defect; uterus without abnormalities. Image obtained from the clinical record, Hospital General de Cancún.

An intraoperative gynecology consult recommended only defect closure, with no indication for hysterectomy. Complete intestinal reduction was achieved, with viable loops and preserved peristalsis. The vaginal defect was repaired with continuous absorbable suture, followed by closure of the Douglas pouch peritoneum with inverting sutures. Standard abdominal wall closure was performed.

On postoperative day six, the patient developed intestinal obstruction. Reoperation revealed lax adhesions compromising bowel transit, which were released without need for further procedures. Recovery was favorable, and she was discharged on postoperative day five without complications.

DISCUSSION

Vaginal evisceration is an uncommon surgical emergency defined as protrusion of pelvic or abdominal viscera through a vaginal wall defect. Since 1864, fewer than 100 cases have been reported. Its estimated incidence is 0.032%–1.2% following procedures such as hysterectomy, trachelectomy, or upper vaginectomy, with a mortality rate of 5.6%.¹²

It is more frequent in postmenopausal women, especially with prior hysterectomy or pelvic organ prolapse. Vaginal atrophy is an important risk factor due to hypoestrogenism, chronic ischemia, and pelvic floor weakening. Smoking, radiation,

and collagen disorders also contribute.⁸ Multiparous postmenopausal women often present ligament laxity and pelvic floor weakness leading to perineal descent of abdominopelvic organs. However, occurrence of a peritoneal defect in the Douglas pouch, producing an internal hernia combined with a vaginal apex defect causing evisceration, is extremely rare without trauma or surgery.³

Symptoms depend on defect size and bowel viability, usually including vaginal pain, bleeding, and discharge. Imaging is not recommended in evident bowel evisceration, though ultrasound can be used in surveillance and postoperative monitoring for intra-abdominal fluid or bowel compromise.⁵ The cornerstone of treatment is early intervention, including gentle reduction of the bowel into the peritoneal cavity and vaginal packing with moist gauze. If reduction is impossible, the bowel must be covered with moist gauze and definitive surgery performed. Delayed intervention increases the risk of ischemia, necrosis, sepsis, and death.²

Surgical repair may be performed via vaginal, abdominal, or abdominovaginal approaches. Laparoscopic abdominal reduction with vaginal repair may reduce recurrence. Vaginal repair is suitable in selected cases without peritonitis, ischemia, or strangulation, though it limits complete bowel assessment.⁶

Definitive treatment includes correction of pelvic floor weakness during initial surgery. Vaginal defects with necrotic tissue or compromised ligament stumps should be excised and closed with absorbable suture. Nichols and Randall suggest delayed pelvic floor assessment with subsequent repair may be preferable to immediate correction.¹⁰

All vaginal evisceration cases are surgical emergencies. The therapeutic goal is preventing complications such as obstruction, strangulation, ischemia, perforation, necrosis, sepsis, and death. Early reduction—vaginal if feasible, or abdominal when edema or technical difficulty exists—followed by immediate vaginal defect repair, is essential.

In this case, absence of prior gynecologic surgery suggests pelvic floor weakness from chronic postmenopausal tissue changes as a predisposing factor. Initial management included fluid therapy, prophylactic antibiotics, and bowel irrigation. Manual reduction failed due to edema, requiring laparotomy. Postoperative bowel obstruction was resolved surgically, with satisfactory outcome.

CONCLUSION

Spontaneous vaginal evisceration is a rare but potentially life-threatening surgical emergency requiring immediate intervention. This case highlights the need to consider it in postmenopausal women, even without surgical history, especially in secondary-level hospitals with limited access to tertiary care. The abdominal approach was most appropriate when manual reduction was impossible, allowing full assessment of bowel viability and definitive repair of the vaginal defect. Although complicated by postoperative obstruction, reintervention achieved complete resolution.

Surgical Management of Vaginal Evisceration in a 66-Year-Old Patient at a Secondary Care Hospital: A Case Report

Strengthening institutional protocols and maintaining high clinical suspicion are essential for optimal outcomes.

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